

Constructing a Simple Prime Sieve Representing Consecutive Odd Sums Using Only Basic Algebra

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Abstract

This educational article explores primes through basic high school-level mathematics to construct a simple and intuitive prime-counting function. The focus is on the well-documented property of odd composite numbers which, unlike primes, can be expressed as sums of multiple consecutive odd numbers. From this connection, we derive a basic counting function to test whether an odd number is prime and to determine how many primes lie below a chosen limit X . Because the same composite can appear as several distinct consecutive-odd sums, we also present a method to filter out these repetitions in a basic sieve-like process. All reasoning uses only high school-level math, making the topic suitable for teaching or self-study.

Note: this is an educational exploration, not a research result

Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. Defining Non-Primes through Odd Composites and Squares	2
2.1. Context	2
2.2. From factors to the difference of two squares	2
2.3. Why we ignore even factors	2
2.4. From squares to consecutive odd sums	3
3. Finding an exact formula for primes	4
3.1. Counting All the Numbers Below a Limit	4
3.1.1. Finding the Largest k	4
3.1.2. Finding the Largest n for Each k	4
3.1.3. Counting All Pairs (k, n)	5
3.2. Applying a Filter (Sieve)	5
4. Optimizing efficiency	6
4.1. Efficiency	6
4.2. Approximating the Count Smoothly	6
4.2.1. Evaluating the Integral	6
4.2.2. Leading Behavior and Error Term	7
5. Quick manual check (calculator-friendly)	7
6. Conclusion	7

1. Introduction

The aim is expository and educational rather than a research paper. While the underlying identities are classical, this paper expands on these basic rules to introduce a simple prime-detection expression. This expression is then coupled with a sieve-style expression to enumerate odd composites below a limit X . The work links introductory techniques—consecutive odd numbers, factorization, quadratic forms, and simple series—making it suitable for a first grasp on representing primes. Hopefully, it illustrates how composite numbers can be counted without advanced number theory.

1.1. Notations and conventions

Let us define $\text{sgn}(y)$ as

$$\text{sgn}(y) = \begin{cases} -1 & y < 0 \\ 0 & y = 0 \\ 1 & y > 0 \end{cases}$$

This article assumes $X \in \mathbb{N}$.

Unless stated otherwise, sums run over odd $n \geq 3$.

We take 1 as neither prime nor composite and 2 as prime.

The final prime-counting function will be defined as

$$\pi(X) = \mathbf{1}_{\{X \geq 2\}} + \sum_{\substack{3 \leq n \leq \lfloor X \rfloor \\ n \text{ odd}}} P(n)$$

2. Defining Non-Primes through Odd Composites and Squares

2.1. Context

Let us use our understanding of an odd composite number X (non-prime) defined as a product

$$X = ab$$

where $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$ are odd, $a \leq b$, and $a \neq 1$.

We can then expand this product to show it equals the difference of two perfect squares.

2.2. From factors to the difference of two squares

Let $c, d \in \mathbb{N}$ with $c > d \geq 0$ be such that

$$a = c - d \quad b = c + d$$

Substituting gives

$$X = (c - d)(c + d) = c^2 - d^2$$

So any odd composite can be written as the difference of two squares.

2.3. Why we ignore even factors

If both a and b were even, say $a = 2m$ and $b = 2n$, then

$$X = ab = 4mn = 4c^2 - 4d^2$$

From

$$\frac{X}{4} = c^2 - d^2$$

$X \in \mathbb{N}$ does not imply $c, d \in \mathbb{N}$ since $\frac{X}{4}$ may not be an integer. We therefore ensure X is odd.

2.4. From squares to consecutive odd sums

Recall $n^2 = 1 + 3 + 5 + \cdots + (2n - 1)$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned}c^2 &= 1 + 3 + \cdots + (2d - 1) + (2d + 1) + \cdots + (2c - 1) \\d^2 &= 1 + 3 + \cdots + (2d - 1)\end{aligned}$$

Subtracting cancels the first d terms, giving

$$X = c^2 - d^2 = (2d + 1) + (2d + 3) + \cdots + (2c - 1)$$

The number of terms is

$$n = c - d$$

so

$$X = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} (2d + 2j + 1)$$

Expanding gives

$$X = n(2d + 1) + 2 \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j = n(2d + 1) + n(n - 1)$$

so

$$X = n^2 + 2dn$$

Here d indicates how far along the odd list the sequence starts. It is convenient to begin the starting odd as the k -th odd number, so set $d = k - 1$. Then

$$X = n^2 + 2n(k - 1) = n^2 + 2kn - 2n$$

which gives a function to model all non-primes

$$f(k, n) = n^2 + 2kn - 2n$$

We model this function by plotting points $(k, f(k, n))$. For each k place a point for the k -th odd and for each odd n plot the value produced by a run of length n starting there. Connecting the points with the same n by a thin line shows how the value grows as the start shifts. Vertical stacks at fixed k show all values obtained from runs beginning at that odd. Intersections of lines or overlapping points mark the same integer produced by different (k, n) pairs.

Figure 1: Representation of $f(k, n)$

3. Finding an exact formula for primes

3.1. Counting All the Numbers Below a Limit

We want the number of pairs (k, n) with $f(k, n) \leq X$, in order to count the quantity of nonprime odd numbers under the ceiling X

3.1.1. Finding the Largest k

We will use the smallest n possible $n = 1$, and insert it into $f(k, n)$ which gives

$$f(k, 1) = 2k - 1$$

To stay below X ,

$$2k - 1 \leq X$$

so

$$k_{\max} = \left\lfloor \frac{X + 1}{2} \right\rfloor$$

Here $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function which rounds the number down to its nearest unit

3.1.2. Finding the Largest n for Each k

Now that we know the highest k , let's find a formula for the maximum n with for every k , under that limit excluding every $n = 1$ and, $n = 2 \times l$, for $l \in \mathbb{N}$. We have

$$n^2 + 2n(k - 1) \leq X$$

Which we can rewrite as

$$n^2 + 2n(k - 1) - X = 0$$

We can then solve this quadratic for n by taking its discriminant

$$\Delta = [2(k-1)]^2 + 4X = 4((k-1)^2 + X)$$

Taking the positive root,

$$n_{\max}(k) = \left\lfloor -k + 1 + \sqrt{(k-1)^2 + X} \right\rfloor$$

3.1.3. Counting All Pairs (k, n)

For each k , the valid n -values are $n = 3, 5, 7, \dots, n_{\max}(k)$, so

$$R_k(X) = \max\{0, n_{\max}(k) - 1\}$$

The total count of odd composites up to X is

$$R(X) = \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor (X+1)/2 \rfloor} \max\left\{0, \left\lfloor -k + 1 + \sqrt{(k-1)^2 + X} \right\rfloor - 1\right\}$$

By reindexing the sums getting every k by iterating over all Natural values of $n, n < n_{\max}$, we can get the more efficient expression

$$S(X) = \sum_{\substack{3 \leq n \\ n \text{ odd}}}^{\lfloor \sqrt{X} \rfloor} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{X - m^2}{2m} \right\rfloor + 1 \right)$$

3.2. Applying a Filter (Sieve)

Currently though it may seem that this formula accurately counts prime this is not the case, since some numbers admit multiple factors and can thus be counted more than once (e.g) $105 = (3 \times 5 \times 7) = 33+35+37 = 17+19+21+23+25$. As such we need a reliable way to filter out the redundant numbers. Which we can derive in the following manner. Let $S(X)$ be the unfiltered total number of odds $\leq X$ produced by the single-sum formula. For odd $X - 2$, the interval $]X - 2, X]$ contains exactly one odd integer, namely X . Consequently, the number of non primes can either be 1 or 0. Therefore

$$S(X) - S(X - 2) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } X \text{ is representable as a sum of consecutive odd numbers;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since an odd N is representable as a sum of consecutive odd numbers if and only if N is composite because primes fail to factor into the sum of more than one odd integers, while every odd composite $N = ab$ with a, b odd and $a \neq 1$. Thus, for every $X \geq 3$, We can define a function $C(X)$ such as

$$C(X) = \text{sgn}(S(X) - S(X - 2))$$

Which acts as a filter 0 if X is prime and 1 otherwise; a fully filtered output. This result can then be used to construct a simple prime counter $P(X)$:

$$P(X) = \underbrace{1 - C(X)}_{\text{prime indicator}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} P(X) = 1, & \text{if } X \text{ is prime,} \\ P(X) = 0, & \text{if } X \text{ is composite.} \end{cases}$$

We can then couple it with our filter $P(X)$ for $X \geq 3$ allowing us to define this prime counting function $\pi(X)$ and add 1 to account for 2.

$$\pi(X) = \mathbf{1}_{\{X \geq 2\}} + \sum_{\substack{n=3 \\ n \text{ odd}}}^X P(n)$$

4. Optimizing efficiency

4.1. Efficiency

The computation of $S(X)$ involves a single summation over $m = 3, 5, 7, \dots, \lfloor \sqrt{X} \rfloor$ so it performs $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{X})$ iterations. Each iteration requires a constant number of arithmetic operations and one floor, thus $S(X)$ can be evaluated with a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{X})$ time. The filter $P(X)$ depends only on $S(X)$ and $S(X - 2)$, so computing it keeps that complexity. On the other hand, the prime-counting function,

$$\pi(X) = \mathbf{1}_{\{X \geq 2\}} + \sum_{\substack{n=3 \\ n \text{ odd}}}^X P(n)$$

requires evaluating $P(n)$ for roughly $X/2$ odd arguments, each costing $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{n})$. Hence the total time complexity is

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\sum_{n=1}^X \sqrt{n}\right) = \mathcal{O}(X^{3/2})$$

4.2. Approximating the Count Smoothly

Though the floor terms in $S(X)$ create small discontinuities we will approximate it by replacing $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ by real values as such

$$S(X) \approx \sum_{m=3}^{\lfloor \sqrt{X} \rfloor} \left(\frac{X - m^2}{2m} + 1 \right)$$

We can then replace the summation with a continuous integral

$$S(X) \approx \int_3^{\sqrt{X}} \frac{X - t^2}{2t} dt$$

4.2.1 Evaluating the Integral

First let us split the integrand

$$\frac{X - t^2}{2t} = \frac{X}{2t} - \frac{t}{2}$$

We can then integrate termwise

$$\int \frac{X}{2t} dt = \frac{X}{2} \ln t \quad \int \frac{t}{2} dt = \frac{t^2}{4}$$

Hence

$$S_{\text{cont}}(X) = \frac{1}{2} \left[X \ln t - \frac{t^2}{2} \right]_3^{\sqrt{X}}$$

Substituting bounds yields

$$S_{\text{cont}}(X) = \frac{X}{2} \ln(\sqrt{X}) - \frac{X}{4} - \frac{X}{2} \ln 3 + \frac{9}{4}$$

Which simplifies into

$$S_{\text{cont}}(X) = \frac{X}{4} (\ln X - 1 - 2 \ln 3) + O(1)$$

4.2.2. Leading Behavior and Error Term

We add an error term $O(\sqrt{X})$ which arises because of the potential error of 1 for each of the roughly \sqrt{X} summands which finally gives us

$$S(X)_{\text{approximated}} = \frac{X}{4} (\ln X - 1 - 2 \ln 3) + O(\sqrt{X})$$

5. Quick manual check (calculator-friendly)

Pick odd X and evaluate $S(X) - S(X - 2)$:

$$S(X) = \sum_{\substack{3 \leq m \leq \lfloor \sqrt{X} \rfloor \\ m \text{ odd}}} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{X - m^2}{2m} \right\rfloor + 1 \right)$$

If X is an odd prime, the difference is 0; if X is an odd composite, the difference is 1 (e.g. primes 7, 11, 13, 97; composites 9, 33, 35, 99).

6. Conclusion

Odd composites can always be expressed as differences of squares or as sums of consecutive odds. By tracing this pattern and filtering duplicates, we obtain a compact sieve that reproduces prime behavior without advanced number theory. The approach is simple to compute and easy to visualize, making it useful for introducing sieve ideas in classrooms or informal study. Future work could test how this counting view compares numerically with classical sieves.